

SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOUR SPILL-OVER FROM WORKPLACE TO PRIVATE LIFE: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

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Abstract: The paper seeks to reveal the holistic approach to the sustainable consumption behaviour spill-over from workplace to private life. The results of theoretical research contribute to the development of sustainable consumption theory highlighting the importance of adequate human resource management practices for the spill-over effect. Previous research on the topic indicate their focus on the spill-over across domains, such as water, energy, etc. Consequently, there is a lack of conceptual background for further research, so the aim of the paper is to determine patterns how sustainable consumption behaviour can be spilled-over from workplace to private life. Conceptual framework is based on the proposition that workplace is considered as an inducing source, which can stimulate or draw-back sustainable behaviour both at workplace and in private life. The main findings of theoretical research, herewith the main elements of conceptual model are organizational and private life settings and their interrelation drivers which enable the sustainable consumption behaviour spill-over from workplace to private life.

Keywords: sustainable consumption, consumer behaviour, spill-over, workplace, private life, social settings

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Introduction

The amount of the research on sustainable management proves the importance of this topic for both academics and practitioners. The interdisciplinary nature of sustainability attracts researchers from different areas. Researches from various fields of management are engaged in solving complex problems of sustainable development, related with company financial performance (e.g. Alshehhi et al., 2018), human resource management issues (e.g. Adam, 2018; Stankevičiūtė and Savanevičienė, 2018), environmental issues (e.g. Gupta and Agrawal, 2018). The latter one is closely related to sustainable consumption, which is one of the most discussed topics in management literature in recent years. Despite its popularity, the question how to enhance sustainable consumption behaviour remains unanswered. When dealing with it, research on sustainability-oriented organisational initiatives, which depend on adequate human resource management

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decisions, and consumer behavior at work and in private life becomes of high significance. It becomes important to understand the role of workplace in the context of sustainable consumer behavior enhancement as well as to deepen the knowledge of spill-over phenomenon.

Research on the topic of sustainable consumption behaviour spill-over reveals controversy results, which in most cases require additional studies. Thøgersen and Olander (2003) found a weak spill-over effects between workplace and private life settings under normal conditions. Tudor et al., (2007) examined the relationship between the work and home settings, indicating the strong link between behaviours in these two social settings. Turnbull Loverock and Newell (2012), Muster (2011) in their studies found that workplace can be considered as an important place, accommodating the necessary environment that can encourage behavioural change and further rapid social change. Moreover, both studies point out that the increasing numbers of companies which are engaging in corporate social responsibility activities are promising starting point for promotion of sustainable consumption both in workplace and in private life. Despite the acknowledged positive effect of sustainable consumption spill-over, most of research have focusing on the spill-over across domains, such as consumption of water, energy, food and transportation. Consequently, the results of such research do not reveal the holistic approach to the sustainable consumption spill-over phenomenon and in most cases do not provide the conceptual basis for further research. Only study by Nik Ramli and Naja (2012) offered conceptual paper regarding the sustainable consumption spill-over from workplace to private life, proposing their theoretical framework. In order to understand and to explore properly the effects of sustainable consumption behaviour spill-over from workplace to private life, first of all it is necessary to identify organizational and private life settings which enables the process of spill-over. In our opinion, for the holistic approach to this phenomenon it necessary to identify characteristics of sustainable consumption behaviour at workplace and determinants of sustainable consumption behaviour in the private life. In addition, their interrelations should be clarified. Consequently, the aim of this paper is to determine patterns how sustainable consumption behaviour can be spilled-over from workplace to private life. From the scientific point of view, the paper seeks to contribute to the field of sustainable consumption research as well as to the development of theory of sustainable consumption by revealing the role of human resource management decisions in the development of sustainable consumption.

Conceptualizing Sustainable Consumption at Workplace and in Private Life

Concept of sustainable consumption

The majority of definitions suggest sustainable consumption is a consumption less or consumption in a different way. The main idea is to find the best way to meet our needs without diminishing the planet's natural resources (Jackson, 2006). For example, the use of products and services in a way that minimises the impact on

the environment; reduce water usage, recycle, and manage the energy better (DEFRA, 2008). All these sustainable activities are related to environmental behavior, which reduce impact on the environment (Jackson, 2006). These could be done in a variety of ways as simple as switching the lights off, walking not driving short trips, consuming and recycling sustainable products (Jackson, 2006; DEFRA, 2008). Other definitions along with ecological aspects of sustainable consumption include social and economic aspects by emphasizing that it is important not only how we produce and distribute goods and services, but also how we organise our societies, government policy, and our lives (SCI, 2016). Within this paper we use definition which defines sustainable consumption as a consumption of sustainable products and services, focusing on the aspects that would encourage socially and ecologically oriented sustainable consumption, while maximising the economic opportunities (Seyfang, 2011; European Commission, 2016).

Sustainable consumption in private life and its expression

Household consumption behaviour is an essential part of production-consumption chain, as the consumers make the final choice regarding the goods and services they consume, and their lifestyles define how these influence sustainability practices (Gibson et al., 2013). Consumption can be considered as a functional attempt to improve individual and collective well-being by acquiring the goods and services that are required to meet people's wants and desires (Jackson, 2005). People vary from each other and this is expressed in their actions, which depend on their experiences and ideas about the good life. Their value orientation is important in defining their idea about the good life, for instance, personal, material goods and culture, followed by the capabilities of the physical, social and economic conditions to realise them (Egmond, 2014). Nevertheless, consumeristic society stimulates people to focus on amount of goods and services rather than on consuming right and efficiently (Jackson, 2005; World Economic Forum, 2009). This underlines the need to redefine the consumeristic view, shifting from stuff to value, from quantity to quality, and from products to services (World Economic Forum, 2009). However, it is important to take into account that each consumer chooses goods and services from the available ones in a way to maximise his benefits, considering the constraints of his available income (Jackson, 2005). In view of that, for people to acquire some specific behaviour, it needs to be considered as a worthy behaviour to acquire (Turnbull Loverock and Newell, 2012). Especially, since the behaviour in the household setting is more voluntary-based, also depending on socio-demographic (household size, income level), psychological (attitudes, values and beliefs), and contextual variables such as infrastructure, incentives, and social norms (Jackson, 2006; Staddon et al., 2016; UNEP, 2015).

Sustainable consumption at workplace and its expression

It is essential to consider that each household resident is an individual who is not only part of the household, but also a part of some other kind of institution at different periods of life whether it is a school during childhood, university during

youth, and/or workplace in the adulthood (Muster, 2011). Referring to Muster (2011), *these different organisations play essential role in an individual's everyday life at different life periods, because people live and consume within these social settings, learning new things, establishing routines and supporting peer groups.* The workplace is one of the places where adults spend around one-third of their everyday lives. Each workplace has their own workplace settings including policies, colleagues and general organisational culture, which have an ability to shape people's attitudes and behaviour. Moreover, through the work people develop their skills, relate with others in the common tasks, and contribute to the greater society (Muster, 2011). However, a workplace is also a complex social setting where there is a high interplay amongst individuals that influence employees' sustainable behaviour such as: interactional, situational, cultural and structural aspects (Muster and Schrader, 2011; Muster, 2011). Therefore, only by creating the environment where sustainability is a common objective, it becomes easier for people to learn and engage in everyday sustainable behaviour (UNEP, 2015). Workplace can be perceived as a place for learning, afterwards fostering a part of the living pattern, which can be transferred to their private life setting (Muster, 2011).

Factors Influencing Sustainable Consumption Behaviour at Workplace and in Private Life

According to Staddon et al., (2016) and Blok et al., (2014) the workplace and household behavioural determinants regarding sustainable consumption varies. They suggest that the workplace environmental behaviours depend on both individual determinants like attitude towards the behaviour and organisation-specific influences like social norms and management support to perform the behaviour (Staddon et al., 2016; Adam, 2018). However, the behaviour in the household setting is more voluntary-based, accordingly suggesting that it depends on socio-demographic (household size, income level), psychological (values and attitudes), and situational (infrastructure) variables (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002; Staddon et al., 2016). Moreover, the family cohesion and support are pointed out as highly important factors in voluntary acquiring new behavioural pattern in private life.

Despite different driving factors, the behaviour is performed by the certain person either it is at workplace or at private life setting. Therefore, according to Blok et al., (2014) the individual or internal factors such as social, cognitive and affective, influencing behaviour should stay consistent in both environments. Social factors consist of social norms (ie. personal beliefs on how to act) and group-shared beliefs on how to act. Cognitive factors refer to the environmental awareness and perceived behavioural control. The environmental awareness can be seen as environmental knowledge and the recognition of the environmental problems. Third internal factor is affective which refers to the general values, environmental values and attitudes toward the environment. It is suggested that the attitude toward

environment has great encouragement to act pro-environmentally. These are mutual variables that do not differ considering the setting (see Table 1). However, the external factors are the ones that shape the individual behaviour patterns concerning the setting (Blok et al., 2014). These are situational/ institutional factors, which refer to the required conditions; and infrastructure that need to be available in order to perform the environmental behaviour. For example, the recycling can be done if the necessary waste management services are provided (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002). The poorer the infrastructure the less likely people will be willing to change their behaviour (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002). Moreover, if there is a need for specific services that supports the behavioural actions in the household setting, it can require additional expenses, accordingly the household income plays great role in encouraging the behaviour (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002; Staddon et al., 2016; Salo et al., 2016). Nevertheless, each social setting should address the system where consumption takes place and seek to address the social and physical infrastructure that enables consumption (UNEP, 2015).

Table 1. Main factors influencing the sustainable behaviour at workplace and in private life (Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002; Blok et al., 2014, Staddon et al., 2016; Salo et al., 2016; UNEP, 2015)

Social setting	Factors
Workplace	Individual identity (values, attitude and behaviour) Organisational culture (social norms, management support and colleagues) Infrastructure
Household	Individual identity (values, attitude and behaviour) Socio-demographic aspects (household size, income level) Family/household cohesion and family support Situational aspects (infrastructure and place)

The main mutual factor in these social settings is an individual himself, with his cognitive and affective internal traits, who is consuming energy, water, food and producing waste and pollution. All other factors depend on the social setting, which differ between work and private settings. In a workplace, the management and colleagues assist behaviours, but at private level, it is more related to the household socio-demographic variables and family support. Nonetheless, workplace is a great place to educate people, supporting formation of new attitude and behaviours that could be spilled-over to private life.

Patterns of Sustainable Consumption Behaviour Spill-Over from Workplace to Private Life

Seeking to specify patterns how sustainable consumption behaviour can be spilled-over from workplace to private life the conceptual model was created (Figure 1). The model represent the extension of the ideas proposed by Nik Ramli and Naja

(2012). There are four main interrelated blocks representing the possible change of sustainable consumption behaviour due to proposed spill-over effect and the necessary circumstances for it to occur: 1) organisational settings; 2) private life settings; 3) dimensions of place attachments; 4) the sequence of behavioural change.

Organisational and private life settings

Employees are human beings who learn and develop environmental attitudes and behaviour both in workplace and private life (Muster and Schrader, 2011). Attitude, values and norms identifies person, no matter what social settings the person is in (Nik Ramli and Naja, 2011). The social setting where a person has to suppress his identity, adapting to the situation, it could raise conflict and cause a disturbed inner feeling (Nik Ramli and Naja, 2011). Accordingly, people are expected to have a strong desire to be consistent in their attitudes, beliefs, words, and behaviours, developing a work-life balance (Nik Ramli and Naja, 2011; Muster and Schrader, 2011). In view of that, the workplace could be a great starting point of the positive spill-over process (Muster, 2011), generating positive influences that would encourage environmentally-friendly behaviour both in workplace and in the private life (Muster and Schrader, 2011).

Figure 1. Theoretical model of the sustainable consumption behavioural spill-over from workplace to private life (Nik Ramli and Naja, 2012, p.1063; Scannell and Gifford, 2010; Klade et al., 2013; Nik Ramli and Wahid, 2012)

Organisational/workplace settings and private life settings were discussed in detailed above in the paper. Everyday settings are convenient for establishing and promoting sustainable consumption behavioural patterns, particularly, since in the workplace setting individuals are free of private and/or household responsibilities and interruptions, which are great in developing *learning atmosphere* (Klade et al., 2013; Muster, 2011). However, Klade et al., (2013) points out that the first precondition for successful spill-over is good atmosphere that promotes understanding and good communication between the colleagues within the workplace. Subsequently, if the organisational environment is good for fostering a sustainable behaviour, two important long-term driven approaches can be used to cultivate learning in order to obtain good spill-over effects: “learning through examples” and “learning by doing” (Klade et al, 2013). Firstly, “*learning through examples*” which works as emulation and imitation (Klade et al., 2013). This can be encouraged from two sides: the human resource management and the colleagues. Secondly, “*learning by doing*” should be encouraged by daily life routines within the workplace (Klade et al., 2013). It is important that these sustainable practices are repeated and trained in order for them to become habitual (Klade et al., 2013; Nik Ramli and Naja, 2012). People’s everyday lives are filled with repetitive activities which turn into embedded habits, allowing to perform routine actions with little or no consideration (Jackson, 2005). Kollmuss and Agyeman (2002) highlight the lack of *infrastructure* available in the private setting could be highly important factor that could constraint people from their intended behaviour. Moreover, Turnbull Loverock and Newell (2012) underlined that some environmental behaviours could be associated with workplace but not with the home setting, therefore not transferring across. Whereas, Muster and Schrader (2011) suggests that behaviour with problematic environmental effects in one social setting could generate or strengthen similar behaviour in the other setting. Despite that, every employee is an individual who is influenced by their personal environmental knowledge, experiences and other social groups including their family and household members (Jackson, 2006; Muster and Schrader, 2011).

Dimensions of place attachments

The third block of the model (see Figure 1), i.e. ‘place attachment dimensions’, is based on three-dimensional framework of place attachment proposed by Scannell and Gifford (2010) in their ‘tripartite model’. The importance of developing place attachment is argued by Anton and Lawrence (2014), who state “communities comprised of highly attached people are more likely to work together to achieve a desired outcome, such as protecting the environment” (Anton and Lawrence, 2014, p.452). Scannell and Gifford (2013) emphasized the benefits of place attachment for promoting concern with environmental issues. Nik Ramli and Naja (2012) used

the Place Attachment Theory in order to explain the positive spill-over process from a workplace to private life. The theory refers to the emotional bond between person and a place which progress through emotional connection, meaning and understanding developed over a period of time (Wolf et al., 2014). The attachment dimensions may overlap but they are also separable. The process dimensions of place attachment consider the way an individual and groups relate to a place as affect, cognitions and behaviour (Scannell and Gifford, 2010). In view of that, a sustainable workplace setting can intensify the sense of environmental responsibility through employee bond to a place (Wolf et al., 2014). For that reason, Nik Ramli and Naja (2012) believe that the workplace attachment could be an important factor, which would be rising the cognitive dissonance regarding the sustainable behavioural patterns in a private life. Therefore, by fostering the sustainable workplace, there is a great possibility for a successful sustainable consumption behaviour spill-over.

The sequence of behavioural change

At the bottom of the model four behavioural constructs are placed in order *to explain the sequence of behavioural change, i.e. behaviour at workplace, attitude formation, dissonance formation and behaviour in private life (named as target behaviour)* (see Figure 1).

Thøgersen (2012) found that behaviour have a direct positive influence on attitudes. He argues that actual behaviour in one domain of sustainable consumption improved the attitudes towards pro-environmental behaviour in general, because of changing attitudes towards sustainable consumption. *The idea proposed by Nik Ramli and Naja's (2012) is that the formation of new attitude will start the spill-over process.* Attitudes are complex combination of personality, beliefs, values, behaviour and motivations, and they result from learning, observing others, and individual's personal experience with other people and situations, influencing people's decisions, guiding their behaviour and influencing what they remember (Pickens, 2005). Social environment plays an important role in providing a person with a sense of self-meaning and influencing social behaviour, which reflects role-associated aspects of self (Hogg et al., 1995). Nik Ramli and Naja (2012) use *Social Identity Theory* to explain the social or group pressure on individuals in a workplace setting which can play a great role in an attitude and norm development, because individuals as group members adopt the group membership as a part of their self-concept. Each of these memberships defines how one should think, feel and behave. Group members are strongly motivated to embrace behavioural strategies for reaching or maintaining in-group (Hogg et al., 1995). Accordingly, it allows interpreting the process of categorising oneself in terms of a particular group membership that would further encourage greater commitment to addressing environmental problems (Fielding and Hornsey, 2016). The *Cognitive Dissonance Theory* suggests that individuals tend to seek consistency in their cognitions, which are: knowledge, beliefs and opinions (Festinger, 1957, cited in Jackson, 2005). Therefore, an individual cannot have two

personalities that switch in regard to the social situation, as it would conflict and cause a disturbed inner feeling, i.e. cognitive dissonance (Nik Ramli and Naja, 2012). People experience the dissonance mainly in a social context, therefore, this context in which an individual behaves need to be considered in order to explain the contradictions in their beliefs (McKimmie, 2015). When the dissonance in the individual's perceptions arise, the individual strives to eliminate this inconsistency. This dissonance can be resolved in one of the three basic ways: change beliefs, change actions, and change perception of action (Festinger, 1957, cited in Jackson, 2005). Nevertheless, Wicklund and Brehm (1976) discuss that the theory does not assure that an individual will successfully reduce or eliminate dissonance, however, it certainly motivates to reduce it. Thøgersen (2012) agrees that cognitive dissonance may lead to the positive behavioural spill-over, primarily when an individual feel morally obligated to act in an environmentally responsible way. The greater the pro-environmental values and norms, the greater desire to avoid behavioural inconsistencies. On the other hand Nik Ramli and Naja (2012) argues that Social Identity Theory and Place Attachment Theory are the ones which can greatly explain the arousal of the cognitive dissonance, therefore, supporting pro-environmental spill-over phenomenon from a workplace to private life setting. Referring to the above it is believed that sustainable behavior in a workplace will lead to a development of a new attitude which will further arise dissonance between workplace and private life behavioural patterns.

Summarising, workplace has been recognised as a good place for learning and fostering a part of the living pattern which could be taken over to private life. The main aim is to create new habits, by rising awareness to a conscious level where people can evaluate the principles of new behaviour. Referring to Nik Ramli and Naja (2012), Scannell and Gifford (2013) proposed explanation of place attachment it is believed that the workplace attachment could be an important factor which would be rising the cognitive dissonance regarding the sustainable behavioural patterns in a private life. Accordingly, in private life, family related determinants should be considered with the situational aspects that highly influence individual behaviour (Nik Ramli and Wahid, 2012). Consequently, considering both ends of process, it could give more insights of spill-over process and support the explanation of positive spill-over outcome (see Figure 1). If this spill-over from workplace to private life will be successfully justified, this will allow to reinforce change toward sustainable consumption, helping authorities towards sustainable development.

Conclusions

Literature analysis let us identify various determinants of sustainable consumption behaviour that need to be considered in order to understand the drivers of sustainable consumption behaviour spill-over from workplace to private life. Workplace should be considered as an environmental, which has a crucial impact

on the favourable sustainable consumption behaviour first of all at workplace and after that for transferring it to private life.

Literature analysis revealed various determinants that encourage spill-over of sustainable consumption behavior. It is supposed that managerial support of employees to act in sustainable manner has a strong effect on sustainable behaviour in workplace. It is argued that two long-term driven approaches can be used to cultivate learning in order to obtain positive spill-over effect: “learning through examples” and “learning by doing”.

After the thorough analysis of scientific literature, the conceptual framework of sustainable consumption behaviour spill-over from workplace to private life is created. It encompasses our theoretical findings and gives a detailed description of the patterns of how sustainable consumption can be spilled-over from workplace social setting to private life. The spill-over process starts with sustainable behaviour at work which is fostered by institution in workplace. Further, the learned behaviour from workplace would lead to new attitude formation, creating dissonance and conclude as target behaviour in private life.

The spill-over process is based on dissonance. People are expected to have a strong desire to be consistent in their attitudes, beliefs, words, and behaviour, thus seeking consistency in their cognitions. It is presumed that only by creating the environment where sustainability is a common objective, it will become easier for people to learn and engage in everyday sustainable consumption behaviour. This behaviour could become a daily routine after a while, and habits gained during it could be transferred to other social setting, i.e. private life. The conceptual model explaining sustainable consumption behaviour spill-over from workplace to private life could be treated as a methodical basis not only for further research, but also for the managers.

The research results provide some useful insights for human resource managers who deal with issues of sustainable management in various industry sectors. First, a necessary infrastructure should be developed inside the company, which would foster waste sorting, energy saving, etc. Second, clear communication about sustainable consumption initiatives inside of a company is necessary, expressing the role of management in supporting employees by “learning through examples” and “learning by doing”. Third, “learning through examples” requires all levels of managers being educated how to facilitate sustainable consumption at workplace, i.e. how to encourage employees in acquiring sustainable consumption behavioural patterns and activities. Only the complex of managerial decisions would enable sustainable consumption behaviour at workplace and then its spill-over to private life.

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ROZPRZESTRZENIANIA SIĘ ZACHOWAŃ ZRÓWNOWAŻONEJ KONSUMPCJI Z MIEJSCA PRACY DO ŻYCIA PRYWATNEGO: RAMY KONCEPCYJNE

Streszczenie: Artykuł ma na celu ukazanie holistycznego podejścia do zrównoważonych zachowań konsumpcyjnych, które przenikają z miejsca pracy do życia prywatnego. Wyniki badań teoretycznych przyczyniają się do rozwoju teorii zrównoważonej konsumpcji, podkreślając znaczenie odpowiednich praktyk zarządzania zasobami ludzkimi dla efektu mnożnikowego. Wcześniejsze badania na ten temat wskazują, że koncentrują się one na rozprzestrzenianiu się między domenami, takimi jak woda, energia itp. W konsekwencji brakuje konceptualnego tła dla dalszych badań, więc celem artykułu jest określenie wzorców zrównoważonej konsumpcji zachowania, które można przenieść z miejsca pracy na życie prywatne. Ramy koncepcyjne opierają się na założeniu, że miejsce pracy jest uważane za źródło pobudzające, które może stymulować lub cofać zrównoważone zachowania zarówno w miejscu pracy, jak i w życiu prywatnym. Główne wyniki badań teoretycznych, a tym samym główne elementy modelu koncepcyjnego, to ustawienia organizacyjne i prywatne oraz ich wzajemne powiązania, które umożliwiają rozprzestrzenianie się zrównoważonych zachowań konsumpcyjnych z miejsca pracy na życie prywatne.

Słowa kluczowe: zrównoważona konsumpcja, zachowania konsumentów, oddziaływanie pośrednie, miejsce pracy, życie prywatne, otoczenie społeczne.

可持续消费行为溢出 - 从工作场所到私人生活：概念框架

摘要：本文试图揭示从工作场所到私人生活的可持续消费行为溢出的整体方法。理论研究的结果有助于可持续消费理论的发展，突出了充分的人力资源管理实践对溢出效应的重要性。以前关于该主题的研究表明他们关注的是跨领域的溢出，例如水，能源等。因此，缺乏进一步研究的概念背景，因此本文的目的是确定可持续消费的模式。行为可以从工作场所蔓延到私人生活。概念框架基于这样的介词，即工作场所被视为诱导源，可以刺激或消除工作场所和私人生活中的可持续行为。理论研究的主要发现，概念模型的主要元素是组织和私人生活环境及其相互关联的驱动因素，使可持续消费行为从工作场所蔓延到私人生活。

关键词：可持续消费，消费者行为，外溢，工作场所，私人生活，社会环境。